

Implementing PIDs at your Institution: Checklist for Success

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NEW TO PIDS, START HERE!

What are Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)?

- A PID is both a unique label (a code or number) for and a long-lasting reference to a *research entity*, like a Person, Place, or Thing. It's associated with additional information (known as 'metadata') about that person, place, or thing. For example, a PID for a journal article (a thing) would be associated with metadata such as the author's name (a person) and their professional affiliation (a place).
- PIDs help to **Disambiguate** the identity of each entity, **Connect** together those entities, and enable their **Interoperability** across software systems/platforms
- PIDs are often persistent with the support of central **PID Registration Agencies**, including [ORCID](#), [DataCite](#), [Crossref](#), [ROR](#), and more!

Why do PIDs matter?

- PIDs help scholars to Save Time and Reduce Administrative Burden
- PIDs support [Open Science](#) and the [FAIR Principles](#)
- PIDs demonstrate significant [Return on Investment](#)
- PIDs can help us to assess Research Impact & Tracking

Who is this Roadmap for, what will it help them do?

- Specifically: Implementers within libraries, research offices, and in IT!
- Generally: Anyone interested in PIDs at their institution and across Canada.
- To support PID uptake, use, and integration across Canada
- Beyond the documents linked above, we have developed several helpful **bilingual resources** as part of an [Engagement Toolkit](#), including a [Policy Briefing](#) and a [PID Strategy Pitch](#) – content to help convince decision-makers
- For more on [Canada's PID Strategy](#), check out the [Website](#)

Why ORCID and DataCite?

- We manage member-driven Canadian ORCID and DataCite Consortia
 - Current communities of practice in Canada centre around these consortia
 - These are not the only PIDs or PID Registration Agencies we need to support
- ORCID iDs/DOIs respect [Values/Criteria](#) set by the Canadian PID Community
- Funding provided by the Alliance to significantly offset member fees

Institutional Actions

Step 1: The Basics

What can you do to get started with PIDs at your institution?

Join [ORCID-CA](#) *(if not already a member)*

- Is your organization a member? The U15 are! [Check here](#)
- Institutional membership costs money and sustained membership over time. Download the [Engagement Toolkit](#) to advocate for membership to your decision-makers. Often, but not always, it is the libraries who are supporting the membership cost.
- To join ORCID-CA, contact orcid@crkn.ca to receive the membership form
 - Learn more about [ORCID-CA Fees](#), covered in part by the Alliance
- Join the ORCID-CA [Listserv](#) - open to all, members and non-members alike.
- Get set up in the [ORCID Member Portal](#) once you join!

Join [DCAN](#) *(if not already a member)*

- Is your organization a member? [Check here](#)
- Institutional membership costs money and sustained membership over time (i.e., you are [responsible for long-term stewardship of your DOIs](#)). Download the [Engagement Toolkit](#) to advocate for membership to your decision-makers. Often, but not always, it is the libraries who are supporting the membership cost.

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- Ensure any institutional repositories follow the [Best Practices for DOI Landing Pages](#). DOIs should point to a landing page rather than a direct download, and that landing page should describe the research output, allowing visitors to understand whether it may be useful to them.

If you can no longer share a research output for which you've registered a DOI, the DOI should point to a [Tombstone Page](#) that explains what the output was and why it's no longer accessible.

- To join DCAN, contact datacite@crkn.ca to receive the membership form
- Learn more about [DCAN Fees](#), covered in large part by the Alliance
- Join DataCite Canada [Google Group](#)
- Get set up in [DataCite Fabrica](#) once you join!

Build institutional awareness and commitment

- Encourage scholars to get ORCID iDs (e.g., Libguides, Workshops, Campaigns)!
- Familiarize Champions and Decision-Makers with PIDs.
Are senior administrators in your Research Office, HR, Central IT, and the Library briefed and supportive? For background and arguments, draw on [key Canadian strategy documents](#).
- Create an intra-institutional PID Working Group, including other institutional units, such as the Research Office, HR, Central IT, Departments, the Library, etc.
- If such a group would be premature, identify colleagues with whom you can work through this checklist within your own academic unit.

Configure built-in *ORCID* plugins or integrations for your systems

- If your local library hosts journals on [OJS/OPS](#), you should turn on the ORCID integration. As a certified system, it is extremely easy to configure.
- If your institution has a [DSpace](#) Repository, you should work toward turning on the ORCID integration, which requires at a minimum DSpace 7.X.
- Your Research Office may have a Research Information Management System (RIMS)/Current Research Information System (CRIS), like DSpace-CRIS or Symplectic Elements, both of which have easy-to-configure integrations.
- If you're using different publishing, repository, or reporting systems, consult the [Common ORCID Integrations list](#) by Lyrasis to find out the integration's status.
- Check out ORCID's [Certified Service Provider List](#) for other options; these systems are the easiest to configure out of the box as a new member of ORCID (including OJS). Note: Plenty of integrations do not fall under this category.

Configure built-in [DataCite](#) plugins or integrations for your systems

- Check out [DataCite's Registered Service Provider List](#). These systems are the easiest to configure out of the box, to automate DOI registration.
- If your local library hosts journals on [OJS/OPS](#), you could turn on the DataCite integration, if you don't already have the Crossref tool turned on (see below). This might be particularly helpful for journals serving as conference proceedings.
- If your institution has a [DSpace](#) Repository, you should ensure that you have a process for registering DOIs for certain subsets of deposits.

Consider other PIDs - e.g., do your journals already register DOIs via Crossref?

- Crossref DOIs:** Crossref is another DOI registration agency with a metadata schema more focused on publications than datasets. We do not currently host a Crossref consortium (they don't have the same kind of membership or fee structure as DataCite), but your institution may [engage directly with Crossref](#).
- ROR:** Double check that your institution has a [ROR](#). If not, please submit a [curation request](#) to ROR, if it falls within the [scope](#).
Additionally, consider curating both the information itself (e.g., acronyms, domains, translations) and the relationships among your institutional RORs (e.g., parent-child connections between associated institutions).
- See [Step 3](#) for more details about new and emerging PIDs.

Step 2: So I've done the Basics, What's Next?

ORCID iDs and ORCID-CA

Develop an ORCID work plan for your institution

- If you are struggling to explain the value of ORCID, take some time to understand the [value of ORCID](#) for different stakeholders.
- If you want to encourage ORCID usage at your institution, leverage various [ORCID Reports](#) provided via the [ORCID Member Portal](#).
- Consult ORCID's [Outreach Resources](#)

Use the [ORCID Affiliation Manager](#) to help your scholars build their ORCID Records

Users can add anything to their ORCID Records manually, but using your membership to add information on behalf of your scholars, with their permission, significantly enhances the consistency and credibility of that information.

- Take responsibility for the affiliation information in ORCID tied to your institution. May require additional intra-institutional strategic planning/support.

- See detailed [guide here](#).

- Employment information for Faculty
- Education information for Grad Students (and beyond)
- Other Professional Activities (e.g., Service on a committee)

[Advocate with a Vendor](#) to add or enhance an existing integration

- Research Offices - Use your purchase power, your relationship with commercial vendors, to advocate for more/better integrations in existing RO systems.

Integrate ORCID with a [custom system](#) you manage on campus

- Consult ORCID's [Technical Documentation](#)

DOIs and DataCite Canada (DCAN)

Start [registering DOIs](#) for research objects not covered by integrations you've activated.

- You can manually register DOIs by filling out a form in DataCite Fabrica. For smaller systems without an existing integration, this can be a good way to register DOIs for your research outputs.
- If you use a system with no integration or plugin, consider developing one. This can help you automatically register DOIs with appropriate metadata for research outputs. If you share it with others who use the system, your new tool could be a helpful contribution to the broader Research Data Management ecosystem.

[Follow the Best Practices for Integrators](#)

- Advocate with a Vendor to add or enhance an existing integration.
- Create **Repository Accounts** for local projects, research groups, and centres

Include as much metadata as possible. This increases your outputs' discoverability (including on DataCite Commons); you can also connect outputs to related resources.

- Watch the following video overviews: DataCite Metadata Training [Part 1](#) & [Part 2](#)
 - How to include more metadata depends on how you register DOIs, but it may mean filling optional metadata fields in your collections management software or on Fabrica.
 - An example of [using connection metadata](#) is to include the DOI of the research article for which a dataset was collected in the dataset's metadata.

The ORCID-CA and DCAN Communities of Practice

- Keep your contact info up to date in the [ORCID Member Portal](#) and [DataCite Fabrica](#).
- Join various PID Community Spaces (e.g., Listserv, Mattermost, Slack, Google Groups)
- Members should join the [ORCID-CA](#) and [DCAN](#) Governing Committees! The nomination period occurs in October with Elections as needed in November or December each year.

Beyond ORCID-CA and DCAN

- Build a local PID Community of Practice**
Ideally, working with PIDs would not be done in isolation - think about other parts of your institution and the way you might want your PIDs to interact.

Step 3: Look toward the Future

- Connect the PID Ecosystem**
 - Do your PIDs connect?
 - Are you pushing DOIs and RORs into a scholar's ORCID record?
 - Are you adding ORCID and ROR IDs to DOI metadata, etc?
- Look beyond ORCID iDs and DataCite DOIs**
 - Consider other PID Agency services in Canada: Crossref DOIs - The choice of Crossref, DataCite, or both for DOI registration depends on your use case(s) and their metadata schemas. [DataCite](#) and [Crossref](#) both have pages explaining when to use one, the other, or both services.
 - Consider existing PIDs for other use cases: [Grant IDs](#) (DOIs for funding), [ROR](#)
 - Consider emerging PIDs: [RAiD](#), [RRID](#), [SWIHD](#), [ARKs](#)
- Advocate for other stakeholders to implement and enhance PID uptake in Canada**
We are at a tipping point - if publishers (DOIs), funders (Grant IDs), universities, and others do more with PIDs, the value of PIDs can be realized.

Achievement Unlocked: PID Mastery

- With your work and support, the dream of PIDs can be realized. If you have completed the Checklist for Success, your institution is now a world leader in all things PIDs. You are meaningfully contributing to the research ecosystem, but there is always more to do!
- Keep your eyes open for more guidance and documentation related to Canada's PID Strategy. This document is, in some ways, a living document - the Strategy will evolve!
- For more information, or to discuss any elements of this Checklist, please contact CRKN and Alliance staff at orcid@crkn.ca or datacite@crkn.ca

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